

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL CLASSES.

Sheralievna Nasiba Alimkulovna

Independent researcher of the
Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute
nasibasheraliyeva23@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarbiya fanini o'qitishda, umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarni "Tarbiya" fanini o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilarning milliy qadriyatlarga qiziqishlarini rivojlantirish va qiziqtirish hisoblanib, "Tarbiya" fanini o'qitish jarayonida umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarida milliy qadriyatlarga qiziqishlarini shakllantirish bo'yicha falsafiy, psixologik, pedagogik, didaktik, metodik, adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish hamda "Tarbiya" fanini o'qitish asosida umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarida milliy qadriyatlarga qiziqishlarini shakllantirishning didaktik ta'minotini takomillashtirish va umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarining o'quv-tarbiyaviy jarayonlarini kompetentsiyaviy yondashuv asosida takomillashtirish" hamda o'quvchilariga tarbiya darslarini samarali tashkil etishda o'quvchilarning kereaktiv fikri haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Annotation: in this article, the subject of future upbringing in general secondary education schools is considered to develop and interest students in national values in the process of teaching teachers the subject of "upbringing", and in the process of teaching the subject of "upbringing" to form their interests in national values in students of general secondary education schools, philosophical, psychological, pedagogical, didactic, methodological, based on the analysis of literature and the teaching of the subject "upbringing", students' kereactive opinion was reflected in improving the didactic provision of the formation of their interest in national values in students of general secondary schools and improving the educational processes of students of general secondary schools on a competency approach, and in the effective organization of educational classes for students.

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматривается предмет воспитания будущего в школах общего среднего образования для развития интереса учащихся к национальным ценностям в процессе преподавания преподавателями предмета "воспитание", а также в процессе преподавания предмета "воспитание" для формирования у учащихся интереса к национальным ценностям школ общего среднего образования,

философских, психологических, педагогических, дидактических, методологических, основанных на анализе литературы и преподавании предмета “воспитание”, активное мнение студентов нашло отражение в совершенствовании дидактического обеспечения формирования интереса к национальным ценностям у учащихся общеобразовательных средних школ и совершенствовании образовательных процессов учащихся общеобразовательных средних школ на основе компетентностного подхода, а также в эффективной организации образовательных занятий для учащихся.

Kalit so‘z: Tarbiya, ta’lim, ahloq, intelektual, qobiliyat, avlod, pedagogika, shaxs, intizom, metodik, germenevtik.

Keyword: upbringing, education, morality, intellectual, ability, generation, pedagogy, personality, discipline, methodical, hermeneutic.

Ключевое слово: воспитание, образование, интеллектуальность, способности, поколение, педагогика, личность, дисциплинарный, герменевтический.

The perfect upbringing of the younger generation has been the greatest goodwill of mankind. In order for this intention to come true, it is required that all segments of society actively participate. People of such a dream are sages of the lands belonging to the age-old Enlightenment, culture-the most moderate intellectuals, the dargah of enlightenment and culture. Among them, it is clear to everyone that our ancestors, who lived on the so-called muazzam land of Uzbekistan, had their place and great prestige. This is a fact recognized by the world community. We can provide a lot of evidence from the history of our people regarding the upbringing of a harmonious generation. President Sh. M. Mirziyoev rated the grown, adult youth as a harmonious generation. Even in reality, those who give their lives for their homeland, nationality and people, their intelligence, energy, if necessary, are representatives of a harmonious generation. As a result of the radical reform of the system of continuing education in our country, a special system of teacher training was established, especially as a result of extensive reforms on the preparation of primary school teachers for professional activities and continuous improvement of their skills.

Pedagogical and psychological factors of educating students as a harmonious personality are a complex, regularly purposefully carried out pedagogical process. On the initiative of President.Sh.M.Mirziyoev, state programs were adopted on the basis of special decisions of our government in

order to carry out large-scale activities aimed at raising a healthy generation, forming a spiritually mature, morally pure, intellectually strong, knowledgeable, physically strong, comprehensively matured personality, and in the process of their implementation, grandiose works are carried out. 28.01.2022 PF-60 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2022 — The decree on the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2026, adopted by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5712 of April 29, 2019 "on the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"...students from a young age are tasked with forming a healthy, strong and influential motivation to study and to choose a profession, independently plan professional growth, develop the ability to master modern professions, in higher pedagogical education, it is important to develop the theoretical foundations for improving the system of training future teachers for the activities of moral education for students and to formulate practical and methodological recommendations.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on state youth policy" of September 14, 2016, PQ-3138 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 18, 2017 "on comprehensive measures to improve the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan", This dissertation serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks set out in PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 on the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and PF-5712 of April 29, 2019 on the approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. The upbringing of young people as a harmonious person depends on the unique works of our great allomas and their OGE, and the founders of our rich spiritual heritage in this husus are Beruniy, Ibn Sina, Kaykovus, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Amir Temur, Husayn Voiz Koshifiy, Navoi, Abdullah Avlani and other allomas, the study of the great services of our society and its implementation is an urgent task of today, especially the discipline of upbringing. The socio-pedagogical essence of this problem is M. Quranov, Q. Munavvarov H. Ibragimov, H. Abdukarimov, R. Ishmukhammedov, N. Muslimov, Sh. Sharipov O. Suvanov, Sh. , Abdullaeva Egamberdieva, D. Rozieva, B. Abdullaeva, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, R. Movlonova, M. Haydarov, T. Hasanov, O. Khasanboeva, Ya. Nurumbekova, Sh. Olimov, Sh. In the scientific works of the likes of Kenjaev, the content of the upbringing of a harmonious personality is theoretically covered, such as Labor, spiritual and moral education of young people, conscious discipline, friendship, comradeship, etc. S. Sharapova M. Yusupov Z. Ibragimova N. In their scientific

research work, the tilyabovas also studied the content of physical education, the upbringing of children in educational institutions and the formation of sophistication, spiritual and moral feelings in them.

But the effective organization of educational lessons under study was not considered as a holistic scientific problem. Education of students as a competent person is a tool in which the role and place of the student and the educator-teacher are not specially researched. Especially in the solution to this problem, the essence of the scientific and theoretical aspects of innovative technologies is not laid on a scientific basis. New pedagogical technologies and their specific solutions have not been found in this direction. It is slow to fully realize the position of the student as a free person in the world of upbringing. Still, in the topic of pedagogical and psychological factors of the education of students as a harmonious person, inconsistency, forced obedience in the place of conscious discipline, passivity in the place of activity are prominent. These issues, waiting for their own solution, determine how relevant the problem is. Aimed at effective use of modern interactive teaching technologies in teaching “upbringing” in general secondary schools, information educational resources of the internet network for teachers and students and a mobile application, a methodological manual for teachers of “upbringing”, a scientifically-theoretically enriched teaching manual for future teachers on the subject “methodology for teaching upbringing in secondary schools” has been created. On the basis of technologies for improving the effectiveness of teaching “upbringing” in general secondary schools, interactive lesson developments of teaching “upbringing” in general secondary schools were developed, experimental and test work was carried out to improve the effectiveness of teaching “upbringing” in general secondary schools, proposals and recommendations were developed.

Clarification of interest in national values in students of general secondary education schools by prioritizing pedagogical transformation processes with andrological, acmeological, communicative paradigms of systemic, activity-oriented, reflexive, hermeneutic, synergistic approaches to the organization of the educational process of their interest in national values in students by teaching “upbringing” in general secondary schools based on practical proposal and research results developed, on the basis of a competency approach, proposals and recommendations for improving the methodological aspects of the systematization of educational materials on the teaching of “upbringing” by directly accounting for the stability of inter-disciplinary and internal integration of educational content with educational processes of educational competence,

communicative, universal, cognitive, informational work, are embedded in the content of the instruction manual “methodology for teaching In the process of upbringing, it is extremely important to properly organize the life and activities of children pedagogically. In the process of activity, the child has a certain attitude towards educational influences coming from outside. This attitude expresses the inner needs and desires of the individual. When the discipline began to be used as a textbook, the tasks assigned to students of future teachers also began to be given in a special way. From the children's textbook, an event that takes place in everyday life, the events perform together with their parents through various rucksacks. The textbook also includes rukons, where homework is done together with family members. As a teaching textbook, which is carried out together with the teacher's parents, the teacher is increasing his interest in science. Future teachers are widely introduced to this textbook in the process of practice. The textbook is one of the much-needed methodological manuals for future teachers and is a methodological manual that provides a great opportunity for students to quickly find a language in the process of conducting lessons. At present ,the textbook of upbringing for students of grades 1-11 of our general and Educational Schools is carried out on the basis of our national traditions,lessons are taught to students ,enriched with various topics and topics related to family, parents, friendship, patriotism and attitude towards our national heritage of the animal world. In conclusion, the role of good upbringing in the family and society in the future development of our children as perfect people is incomparable.

Conclusion : The more civilized, polite parents, mentors, leaders, and older adults are, the more polite individuals growing up in that society and environment. This kind of sermas'uliyat is an urgent matter of today to carry out social work, that is, to be a good example and role model for our young people with our own behavior so that they can grow up to be polite, sympathetic, conscientious people.

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